

IFRS Implementation in UK Organizations

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ABSTRACT

Purpose – This study examines the practical challenges faced by UK organizations when implementing International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), a mandatory framework designed to enhance transparency and consistency in financial reporting across jurisdictions.

Methodology/Approach – A quantitative research design was employed, utilizing survey data collected from 70 financial professionals working in UK-based organizations. The survey targeted practitioners across small, regional, and multinational firms. Descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and t-tests were used to test the hypothesis that IFRS standards are complicated and pose significant implementation challenges for adopting organizations.

Findings – The results support the null hypothesis, confirming that organizations face significant issues when adopting IFRS. Specifically, the most commonly cited challenges were transition problems (32.86%), lack of expertise (22.86%), time constraints (17.14%), and higher costs (27.14%). The findings indicate that these challenges persist across organizations of different sizes, though larger multinational firms reported relatively smoother transitions compared to smaller entities.

Conclusion – The research highlights the need for foundational capacity-building measures and strategic planning to facilitate smoother IFRS adoption. Organizations should invest in targeted training programs, seek professional guidance, and allocate sufficient resources for implementation.

Keywords: IFRS, UK GAAP, IASB, financial reporting, accounting standards

JEL Codes: M41, M48, G38

List of Keywords

IFRS: International Financial Reporting Standards

IASB: International Accounting Standard Board

GAAP: Generally Accepted Accounting Principles

IAS: International Accounting Standards

FASB: Financial Accounting Standard Board

EITF: Emerging Issues Task Force

EBITDA: Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation, and Amortization

LIFO: Last In First Out

FIFO: First In First Out

Acknowledgement

I acknowledge the contributions of my friends and my teachers for developing this research project. I also show my heartfelt gratitude to the persons that have cooperated with me to find relaxing journals and scholarly articles. I also acknowledge the help that I have from my departmental head. My academic supervisor has helped me to find out this most relevant research topic. My family have helped me to gain practical and educational knowledge that would help me carry out the research.

Table of Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background	1
1.2 Aim and Objectives	1
1.3 Research Questions	1
1.4 Research Hypothesis	2
1.5 Rationale	2
1.6 Dissertation Structure	3
2. Literature Review	4
2.1 Conceptual Framework	4
2.2 Critical Analysis	5
2.2.1 Variable 1: Accounting principles such as GAAP, IFRS is a complicated process and has a large number of cost constraints	5
2.3.3 Variable 3: Impact of IFRS in financial statements	9
2.3.4 Variable 4: Relationship between IFRS, profitability and equity	10
2.3.5 Variable 5: Theoretical underpinning	13
<i>Figure 2.4.1: Recognition and measurement concept</i>	15
2.5 Literature gap	15
2.6 Summary	15
3: Research Methodology	16
3.1 Introduction	16
3.2 Research outline	16
3.3 Research Philosophy	17
3.4 Research Approach	17

3.5 Research Design	19
3.6 Data Collection Method	20
3.7 Data Analysis	20
3.8 Ethical Consideration	21
3.9 Timeline	21
3.10 Summary	22
Chapter 4: Result and Analysis	22
4.1 Introduction	22
4.2 Quantitative Analysis	22
Responses	22
Rating on the basis of responses	22
Number of responses	22
Percentage (%)	22
Total number of respondents	22
4.3 Descriptive Analysis	34
4.3.1 Mean	34
4.3.2 Median	35
4.3.3 Mode	35
4.3.4 Standard Deviation	35
4.3.5 Regression Analysis	35
4.4 Hypothesis Testing	37
4.5 Summary of result	45
Chapter 5: Discussion of Results	45
Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendation	50

6.1 Conclusion	50
6.2 Linking with objective	51
6.2.1 Objective 1: To identify the issues that can arise while implementing the IFRS standards	51
6.2.2 Objective 2: To implement the effects of IFRS on the profitability and equity position of the organization	51
6.2.3 Objective 3: To determine the role-played by accounting institutes in formulating these standards	52
6.2.4 Objective 4: To explore the process of adaptation of the IFRS in the UK	52
6.2.5 Objective 5: To assess the costs and other problems that may arise through the implementation of IFRS	52
6.3 Limitations	53
6.4 Recommendations	53
6.5 Future Scope	53
References	55

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Accounting activities require rigorous regulation to prevent fraudulent practices. The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) issued the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) to regulate financial and accounting practices globally. The primary aim of IFRS is to increase transparency in financial activities and their presentation. IFRS ensures the preparation of financial reports with reasonable consistency across industries and countries. Prior to IFRS, the International Accounting Standards (IAS) were issued by the IASB, with the same objectives; IAS was replaced by IFRS in 2001. In the UK, the Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) are followed, specifically UK GAAP – FRS 101 and FRS 102, which form part of the IFRS framework. IFRS was developed to bring consistency, transparency, accountability, and efficiency to financial statements worldwide (Dias, Teles & Duzert, 2018). There are 16 IFRS standards in practice since 2005, each addressing different areas of accounting (Kabir & Rahman, 2018).

Despite these benefits, UK companies often struggle to implement IFRS due to lack of training and education (Mattei & Paoloni, 2019). Implementation is time-consuming, and although financial implications may be modest, systematic changes are highly challenging for both small and large organisations (Collis, Jarvis & Skerratt, 2017). This research focuses on UK companies listed on the London Stock Exchange's main market or FTSE index.

1.2 Aim and Objectives

Aim: To detail the practical implementation of IFRS standards in UK-based companies.

Objectives:

- 1) To identify issues arising while implementing IFRS standards.
- 2) To examine the effects of IFRS on profitability and equity position.
- 3) To determine the role of accounting institutes in formulating these standards.
- 4) To explore the process of IFRS adaptation in the UK.
- 5) To assess costs and other problems arising from IFRS implementation.

1.3 Research Questions

- a) What are the practical implications of implementing IFRS within UK organisations?
- b) How do IFRS impact the financial statements of UK-based organisations?
- c) What issues can organisations face while adopting IFRS?

Figure: 1.3 Research questions

(Prepared by the Author)

1.4 Research Hypothesis

H₀: IFRS standards are complicated, and organisations face different issues while implementing them.

H₁: IFRS standards are not complicated, and organisations face no issues while implementing them.

1.5 Rationale

According to Al-Nasrawi & Thabit (2020), the main issue is that most UK companies lack adequate knowledge or expertise to implement IFRS properly. The transition from GAAP to IFRS is difficult because IFRS is based on principles while GAAP is rule-based. Additionally, IFRS is dynamic and constantly updated (Felski, 2017), requiring continuous adaptation. Over 140 jurisdictions follow IFRS, making it essential for cross-border comparability and transparency (de Moura, Altuwajjri & Gupta, 2020). Given recent accounting frauds (e.g., Patisserie Valerie, Ted Baker), IFRS implementation has become crucial. Post-BREXIT complexities further necessitate an in-depth understanding of IFRS.

#	Name	Is- sued
IFRS 1	<i>First-time Adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards</i>	2008*
IFRS 2	<i>Share-based Payment</i>	2004
IFRS 3	<i>Business Combinations</i>	2008*
IFRS 4	<i>Insurance Contracts</i> <small>Will be superseded by IFRS 17 as of 1 January 2023</small>	2004
IFRS 5	<i>Non-current Assets Held for Sale and Discontinued Operations</i>	2004
IFRS 6	<i>Exploration for and Evaluation of Mineral Resources</i>	2004
IFRS 7	<i>Financial Instruments: Disclosures</i>	2005
IFRS 8	<i>Operating Segments</i>	2006
IFRS 9	<i>Financial Instruments</i>	2014*
IFRS 10	<i>Consolidated Financial Statements</i>	2011
IFRS 11	<i>Joint Arrangements</i>	2011
IFRS 12	<i>Disclosure of Interests in Other Entities</i>	2011
IFRS 13	<i>Fair Value Measurement</i>	2011
IFRS 14	<i>Regulatory Deferral Accounts</i>	2014
IFRS 15	<i>Revenue from Contracts with Customers</i>	2014
IFRS 16	<i>Leases</i>	2016

Figure 1.5: List of IFRS Standards

(Source: Abdullah *et al.*, 2018)

1.6 Dissertation Structure

The research is presented in five sections: introduction, literature review, methodology, results and analysis, and conclusion with recommendations.

Figure 1.7: Dissertation Structure

(Source: Prepared by the Author)

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study positions accounting principles (IFRS, GAAP, IAS), institutional roles, financial statement impacts, and cost constraints as independent variables, with profitability and equity position as dependent variables.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework

(Source: Prepared by the Author)

2.2 Critical Analysis

2.2.1 Variable 1: Accounting principles such as GAAP, IFRS is a complicated process and has a large number of cost constraints

The transition of IFRS did not increase the pervasiveness of earnings management in countries like France and managed to remain constant in UK and Australia. The findings of this study indicate that the transition of IFRS did not leave a remarkable improvement in terms of earnings quality (Hwang, Hur & Kang, 2018). IFRS has been developed by the International Accounting Standards Boards (IASB). There are large numbers of UK companies such as Sainsbury's, HSBC, Royal Dutch Shell and others that are directly impacted by these IFRS standards. In this context, Hashed & Almaqtari (2021) has stated that both in large and small companies only a few key personnel are provided proper training for implementing and monitoring the implementation of IFRS due to cost constraints. Napier & Stadler (2020) thinks that IFRS tends to undermine the qualitative aspect of financial accounting. In the case of IFRS accounting, a large group of companies tend to depend on their auditors, which can sometimes lead to similarity of the processes.

There are two kinds of isomorphism such as coercive isomorphism whereby the government and other regulatory bodies start to interfere in the financial reporting of the entities. However, in the case of mimetic isomorphism, the reporting entities start to model other companies to develop their policies and principles. This comparison can sometimes hamper the qualitative aspects of useful financial information (Abdullah et al., 2018). On the other hand, at certain points, the employees and other staff may pose resistance while adapting to the IFRS standards due to its increased complexity, dynamic and ever-changing regulations and difficulty of implementation. Thus, UK based companies must consider these issues before deciding to transition or adopt IFRS principles.

COMPANIES RANKED BY OPERATING LEASE OBLIGATIONS			
Rank	Company	Industry	Operating Leases (MM)
1	Royal Dutch Shell	Oil & Gas Producers	£18,279.42
2	BP	Oil & Gas Producers	£10,868.59
3	Sainsbury's	Food & Drug Retailers	£10,019.00
4	Vodafone Group	Mobile Telecommunications	£8,621.32
5	International Airlines Group	Travel & Leisure	£6,796.38
6	BT Group	Fixed Line Telecommunications	£6,597.00
7	IWG	Miscellaneous Commercial Services	£5,057.50
8	Associated British Foods	Food Producers	£4,614.00
9	Marks & Spencer	General Retailers	£4,196.00
10	FirstGroup	Other Transportation	£3,622.10
11	Whitbread	Retail hospitality	£3,579.60
12	HSBC	Banks	£3,076.56
13	Tesco	Food & Drug Retailers	£2,599.00
14	BBA Aviation	Investment Trusts/Mutual Funds	£2,576.00
15	Barclays	Banks	£2,536.00
16	TUI Group	Travel & Leisure	£2,311.41
17	Royal Bank of Scotland Group	Banks	£2,279.00
18	Unilever	Personal Goods	£2,182.45
19	Wizz Air	Airlines	£2,111.31
20	Dixons Carphone	Specialty Stores	£2,057.00
21	Lloyds Banking Group	Banks	£2,054.00
22	CRH plc	Construction & Materials	£1,947.25
23	Merlin Entertainments	Movies/Entertainment	£1,897.00
24	Rolls-Royce Holdings	Aerospace & Defence	£1,871.00
25	Next plc	General Retailers	£1,847.70
26	Tritax Big Box REIT	Wholesale Distributors	£1,842.83
27	Travis Perkins	Investment Trusts/Mutual Funds	£1,832.10
28	Greene King	Restaurants	£1,827.10
29	Morrisons	Food & Drug Retailers	£1,769.00
30	BAE Systems	Aerospace & Defense	£1,646.00

Figure 2.3.1: FTSE 350 Companies Implementing IFRS 16 for Lease Liabilities

(Source: Chistopher Merchant, 2019)

Similar situations are also witnessed for UK GAAP. As per the legislation of the UK, all the businesses are required to show a "true and fair view" of the financial statements. Moreover, the UK GAAP lays down a detailed format that a company needs to follow in order to showcase a transparent and faithful view of the financial statements. However, the Generally Accepted Accounting Principles are based on several presumptions such as the company is a going concern, the income and expenses of the enterprise are recorded on an accrual basis, the accounting policies are applied consistently. However, every business does not apply each of these policies and it becomes difficult to align the GAAP principles for these enterprises. Although Elsayed et al. (2021) has stated that the GAAP principles have been successful for the majority of companies. Moreover, transitioning from UK GAAP to UK IFRS has been easy for the

majority of enterprises due to the similarity between these two principles. However, D'Arcy & Tarca (2018) thinks that there are a large number of project issues witnessed while using these GAAP principles. There can be issues with resources, timeline and communication when it comes to both the UK GAAP and UK IFRS. On the other hand, there are a large number of differences between the UK GAAP and the IFRS. For example, as per UK GAAP only a residual value estimate is needed to be made at the time of purchase. However, these principles had made it difficult for investment or real estate companies for assets like ships or aircraft.

Moreover, under UK GAAP, the computer software is mentioned under 'tangible assets', which have to be reallocated to 'intangible assets' as per IFRS principles. Thus, it is evident that the implementation of both the IFRS and GAAP principles affect different business enterprises in different ways. However, the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) is trying to bring parity between these accounting policies and principles. Tutino et al. (2019) has also argued that the majority of UK companies faced difficulties to identify and analyse embedded derivatives. The guidance provided by IFRS 9 has specifically mentioned embedded derivatives to prevent the companies from bypassing the recognition and measurement of derivatives by embedding a derivative with another non-derivative. However, the examples provided by the IASB are mostly applicable to companies associated with financial services. This had created confusions for other companies to understand the impact of these on their financial statements. Moreover, it is found that often the companies have to spend huge amounts to establish the fact that they do have any 'embedded derivatives' that have to be separated from host contracts.

2.2.2 Variable 2: Role of Accounting Institutes in Formulating IFRS, GAAP, IAS

The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) is an independent body of the IFRS foundation having 22 trustees in the IFRS Foundation and 16 members in the IASB board. Martucheli & Pereira Filho (2021) has identified that IASB over the years has been able to ensure a consistent application of the IFRS standards. This board prepares an IASB conceptual framework for assisting in the formulation of consistent and coherent accounting principles. However, Mantzari & Georgiou (2019) has argued that the IASB has in several situations failed to properly formulate business policies. There is a lack of transparency and clarity in the standards issued, which leads to further confusion in the future. Moreover, several studies have shown that in the majority of the cases the value relevance of forecast earnings has reduced under the IFRS system. However, this kind of incident is very rare and in the majority of the situations, the IASB has been able to provide an accurate and less dispersed financial presentation. There are other institutions available, which have similar functions such as the ICAI (Indian Institute of Chartered Accountants of India), ICAB in Bangladesh and many others.

On the other hand, GAAP has been formulated by the Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB), which was established in 1973. It is a privately owned not for profit organization having its organization

in Norwalk, Connecticut. The main mission of this organization is to set the highest quality standards in a robust, comprehensive and inclusive manner. Moreover, the Financial Accounting Foundation (FAF) also oversees the promotion and implementation of standard driven processes. However, the FASB has been faced with a large number of issues with the implementation and application of the GAAP principles. For this purpose, the board has created an EITF group or Emerging Issues Task Force. The main mission of this committee is to help in improving the financial reporting of accounting bodies through the identification, discussion and resolution of issues and other confusions of the companies while applying the GAAP principles.

On the other hand, the IACB in Bangladesh also created a framework for financial reporting and management. The main purpose of this accounting board is to decide the right time to buy, sell or hold equity, to determine taxation policies, to regulate the activities of the accounting entities, to measure the profits and dividends and many other factors. However, the IFRS framework has been formulated to align each of these accounting principles to create a collaborative framework for financial reporting. However, MacGregor Pelikánová & Cvik (2018) has stated that the accounting policies and principles recommended by FASB oftentimes create overstatements or understatements in the financial recordings. For example, in several cases, the accounting principles provided by the FASB compels companies to record the values of assets and revenues at a lower value than the other alternative methods. However, Odo (2018) has negated this notion by stating that IFRS and GAAP principles are applicable for both large companies and small companies. This has tremendously helped the small companies as they can now approach larger enterprises for investment by presenting their financial statements in a globally recognized accounting framework.

On the other hand, Mantzari & Georgiou (2019) has highlighted that there were several occasions when the FASB has failed to consider the point of views of the stakeholders. For example, in the initial stages, there were two methods of accounting for business combinations, such as pooling of interest and purchase price method. However, the FASB has eliminated the pooling of interest method. This has caused several issues for the investors and analysts because of the lack of information regarding this concept. In a survey, the CEO of a well-known company had mentioned that it took them. Thus, it is evident that there are different arguments regarding the role of accounting boards like FASB, IASB and many others.

These accounting bodies have helped in providing clarifications and guidance on the relevant accounting policies. Moreover, these have enabled the companies operating in the UK or operating in other countries to gain easy comparability for their financial statements. However, there also have been instances where these bodies have failed to meet the expectations of different stakeholders of these accounting principles. Oftentimes, the principles established by the IASB, FAF and FASB have increased

the complexity level of financial reporting, which has further led to a difference in the financial projection.

Figure 2.3.2: Structure of IASB

2.3.3 Variable 3: Impact of IFRS in financial statements

According to Hwang, Hur & Kang (2018), the IFRS standards have been able to bring more consistency in the financial statements. However, different IFRS standards impact financial statements in their way. For example, IFRS 15 deals with revenue recognition and as per this standard, only those revenues can be recorded by an entity that has already been transferred to the customers at the transaction price. This standard can impact the financial recordings of rights of return, customer loyalty programs, contract manufacturing and many similar transactions. On the other hand, the new IFRS 16 changes performance indicators like EBITDA, cash flows and the effect of lease covenants (André, 2017). For example, the lease payments are shown both in the cash flow from investment activities and the cash flow from financing activities.

There is no specific way to measure whether the profitability of the companies as per the IFRS standards have improved or reduced. However, it can be said that the accounting procedures have become highly diversified and more detailed under the IFRS standard. However, Howieson (2017) thinks that by implementing the IFRS 16, the debt position of companies tends to increase. A survey on 50 listed

companies that have applied IFRS 16 has shown an increased debt position of €40 to €50 billion. Thus, it is evident that the impact of these standards depends on the size, operations and previous accounting practices of the companies.

Old standard		New standard	
Balance Sheet	FY 20xx	Balance Sheet	FY 20xx
	\$		\$
		Lease assets	xxx
		Lease liabilities	xxx
Income statement	FY 2015	Income statement	FY 2015
	\$		\$
Lease payments	xxx	Low-value/short-term leases	xxx
EBITDA	xxx	EBITDA	xxx
		Depreciation and amortisation	xxx
		Finance cost	xxx
Profit before tax	xxx	Profit before tax	xxx

Figure 2.3.3: Accounting for Leases as per IFRS 16

(Source: Deloitte, 2016)

2.3.4 Variable 4: Relationship between IFRS, profitability and equity

There is a huge difference in the IFRS and UK GAAP accounting standards. In terms of its impact, it has been seen that the IFRS Standards have a 6.66% impact on the profit shown as per the UK-GAAP (D'Arcy & Tarca, 2018). However, the impact on GAAP based equity tends to be negative. In another study, 100 FTSE companies were selected for a survey to determine the impact of IFRS standards on their financial statements. It was seen that out of these 100 companies, 39% of them had seen an increase in their profitability while 23% had seen a decrease in the equity position. However, there is a presumption that there are very few insignificant adjustments made to transition from the UK-GAAP to the IFRS standards. This idea has been argued by other scholars. Bui, Le, & Dao (2020) has argued that the changes in both of

these standards can vary from company to company.

	Mean	SD	Median	Min	Max	Skew	Kurt
Total profit per national GAAP	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	N/A	N/A
<i>IFRS 2</i>	-0.23	32.08	-0.69	-124.32	292.22	6.41	65.95
<i>IFRS 3</i>	29.73	85.57	3.47	-67.47	727.03	5.70	41.29
<i>IFRS 4</i>	0.77	5.47	0.00	-0.70	42.17	7.29	52.41
<i>IFRS 5</i>	0.34	2.80	0.00	-1.82	27.27	8.78	81.12
<i>IAS 1</i>	0.44	3.59	0.00	-0.65	35.00	8.82	81.60
<i>IAS 10</i>	7.45	54.03	0.00	-0.28	532.35	8.82	83.40
<i>IAS 12</i>	-9.51	66.09	0.00	-627.09	34.38	-8.20	72.88
<i>IAS 16</i>	-0.31	1.78	0.00	-13.33	3.42	-5.20	31.99
<i>IAS 17</i>	-4.14	42.30	0.00	-431.82	87.50	-9.50	97.52
<i>IAS 18</i>	-0.16	1.63	0.00	-12.50	3.19	-6.64	47.55
<i>IAS 19</i>	-1.61	12.12	0.00	-72.73	41.27	-3.07	17.26
<i>IAS 21</i>	-2.09	17.41	0.00	-180.28	6.21	-9.97	102.43
<i>IAS 28</i>	0.28	3.34	0.00	-3.11	34.87	10.30	107.84
<i>IAS 31</i>	1.19	15.87	0.00	-62.16	131.82	5.18	46.30
<i>IAS 32</i>	-0.16	1.54	0.00	-16.22	0.00	-10.47	110.06
<i>IAS 36</i>	-0.21	3.44	0.00	-32.43	13.82	-7.07	73.77
<i>IAS 38</i>	6.50	51.38	0.00	-45.45	494.75	8.47	77.42
<i>IAS 39</i>	-1.37	6.73	0.00	-51.99	19.76	-4.84	33.09
<i>IAS 40</i>	38.72	268.91	0.00	-0.13	2,506.70	8.16	69.96
<i>IAS 41</i>	0.83	8.79	0.00	-0.72	92.60	10.53	110.98
<i>IAS 32/IAS 39</i>	10.75	112.05	0.00	-10.34	1,180.17	10.52	110.81
<i>IAS 27, 28 & 31</i>	0.83	8.23	0.00	0.00	86.70	10.51	110.56
Goodwill	0.94	7.00	0.00	-35.47	40.11	1.62	19.58
<i>IFRS 3 & IAS 38</i>	1.05	6.52	0.00	0.00	49.51	6.42	41.57
Other	0.05	9.73	0.00	-43.78	61.42	1.36	18.94
Minority interests	-0.13	0.98	0.00	-7.61	1.81	-6.47	44.90
Reallocations	0.83	8.78	0.00	0.00	92.48	10.54	111.00
Total profit - IFRS	148.51	307.76	106.67	-340.91	2,963.41	7.36	65.27

Figure 2.3.4: IFRS Adjustments to Income Statement

Similarly, Fasan & Marcon (2018) thinks that in the majority of the cases the managers of UK companies tend to misappropriate the reconciliation statements provided to hide price-sensitive information. Despite these issues, it can be mentioned that IFRS standards increase profitability while reducing the equity position of the companies. However, there have been cases where implementing the IFRS standards have reduced profitability as compared to the UK-GAAP. It is said that the changes in the equity position and profitability depend majorly on goodwill accounting. For example, in IFRS 3 goodwill is needed to go through an annual impairment review. However, as per FRS 10, goodwill has a lifetime of a maximum of 20 years and it is amortized throughout its lifetime (Eluyela et al., 2019). Generally, the profits from IFRS 3 will be more than FRS 10. Moreover, the income statements have also reflected that the increase in profits essentially results from the effects of IAS 12, which deals with income taxes. Thus,

it can be concluded that the impact of IFRS on the profitability and equity position is influenced by the types of standards implemented as well as the availability of reconciliation statements.

In the case of GAAP principles, it has been found that it is a standardized set of principles that helps the investors to analyse the profitability and equity position of the companies. The GAAP principles include revenue recognition principles, monetary measurement concept, time assumption, cost principles and separate entity concept (Gornjak, 2020).

These principles are further based on the concept of expense recognition principles, going concern assumption, conservatism convention and full disclosure principle. However, the revenue recognition and its impact on profitability are quite different both in GAAP and IFRS. For example, there are different approaches for preparing balance sheets under GAAP and IFRS principles. For example, the GAAP principles prescribe the accounts to be listed based on their liquidity (Ebaid, 2021). The less liquid assets are presented on the top whereas the current assets are mentioned in the lower segments. However, in IFRS principles, the current assets are shown first followed by the non-current assets. In this context, Guerreiro, Lima Rodrigues & Craig (2021) has argued that the change in the structure of the balance sheet does not impact the profitability of a company. However, in the case of the cash flow statement, the GAAP and IFRS principles provide different sets of rules. For example, the GAAP principles recommend that dividend paid needs to be included in the financial activities whereas the IFRS principles state that the dividends need to be presented under cash flow from operating activities or cash flow from financing activities (Emekaponuzo, Jeremiah & Alfred, 2017). On the other hand, interest paid under GAAP recommends the same under cash flow from operating activities. However, as per IFRS the interest received can be mentioned in either the cash flow from operating activities or cash flow from investing activities.

These differences have created major confusions among the investors, and it has also impacted the profitability and equity position of the companies. Moreover, Napier & Stadler (2020) has argued that there has also been a problem with comparability among the financial statements due to the alternatives provided within the IFRS principles. For example, one company can present dividend paid under financial activities whereas the other company can present the same within the operating activities (Thi, Anh & Tu, 2020). This particular aspect will fluctuate the cash flow statements and also hamper the profitability of the companies.

Elsayed et al. (2021) has also argued that the inventory policy under GAAP and IFRS are also quite different. As per the GAAP principles, there are three kinds of inventory measurement policy such as Last in First Out (LIFO), First in First Out (FIFO) and the weighted average method. However, under the IFRS system, there is only FIFO and the weighted average method. However, this particular change can affect the profitability of the companies as it changes the measurement of both the opening inventories and

closing inventories. Moreover, it also creates difficulty in comparing the financial statements as a company can use either FIFO or the weighted average method. Thus, it can be said that the financial statements are highly affected due to the differences in the policies and principles.

2.3.5 Variable 5: Theoretical underpinning

IASB conceptual framework

The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) develops a framework for financial reporting to provide reference documents for the development and implementation of accounting principles. This provides a consistent approach towards problem-solving and helps in resolving accounting issues that are not otherwise directly addressed within the standards. de Moura, Altuwajiri & Gupta (2020) states that this framework helps investors as well as other stakeholders of companies to understand the purpose of these accounting standards along with their limitations. Felski (2017) has stated that there are five main elements of this framework namely assets, liabilities, income, equities and expenses. Thus, different IFRS standards are developed for these five different elements. For example- IFRS 3 deals with the acquisition of a group of assets, IFRS 13 deals with Fair value measurement and many others.

Figure 2.4: Conceptual Framework of IASB

On the other hand, IFRS 16 deals with lease liabilities and IFRS 15 includes revenue from contracts with customers. Kiliç & Uyar (2017) thinks that formulating different standards for different elements ensures higher consistency and transparency in financial statements disclosures. However, Al-Nasrawi & Thabit (2020) believes that due to the complexities of these standards and their changing policies and procedures, it becomes difficult for the company to implement the same. Moreover, the framework and

all the rules and regulations included within gets updated as per the recent environmental changes. For example- in the post BREXIT situation, the IFRS policies to be adopted by the UK will be different from those already applied by the EU companies (Collis, Jarvis & Skerratt, 2017). It becomes difficult for the general investors to keep track of these changes and oftentimes the clarifying documents get delayed. Thus, the IASB needs to improve its financial reporting framework to ensure transparent and consistent reporting.

Conceptual framework of FASB

The Financial Accounting Standards Board has formulated a conceptual framework to set proper financial policies and to help the members in understanding and application of these principles. In this context, Thi, Anh & Tu (2020) has stated that a conceptual framework is a body of interrelated fundamentals and objectives. It helps the business enterprises to identify the objectives of financial reporting. The main aim of the FASB conceptual framework has always been to provide an understanding of specific terminology, to limit the areas of discretion and judgement, to establish a common ground for discussion and comparison and dealing with conflicts. However, it has to be understood that the conceptual framework does not directly impact the principles of Generally Accepted Accounting Principles. Despite this statement, Napier & Stadler (2020) has argued that several GAAP principles do conflict with the conceptual framework established. For example- museum collections generally are treated as 'Assets' as per the conceptual framework and are presented within the 'Asset' section of the Balance Sheet. However, these assets are not needed to be included in the financial statements as per GAAP principles (Emekaponuzo *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, it is said that the FASB board will get the most benefits out of these conceptual frameworks as it will help them to develop a strong foundation for policy formulation and implementation. It is said that the framework helps in narrowing down the alternative solutions available by eliminating those inconsistent with the recent accounting requirements and global needs of the companies. On the other hand, Gornjak (2020) has also stated that this conceptual framework has increased the credibility of concepts that direct the financial reporting frameworks. These help in developing standards that are internally consistent with the external changes. Moreover, this framework also helps in reducing the political pressures on the users and preparers of the financial statement (Kolesnik, Silska-Gembka & Gierusz, 2019). Thus, it can be stated that the FASB conceptual framework has profoundly changed how financial reporting is managed and monitored by the FASB. However, the FASB needs to make an in-depth analysis of the policies and principles developed based on this framework to mitigate the confusions and differences with other accounting principles.

Figure 2.4.1: Recognition and measurement concept

2.5 Literature gap

All the previous researches have only provided qualitative data regarding the implication of IFRS, its governing bodies and its impact on the financial performance of UK based companies. However, it has failed to provide proper quantitative data regarding the practical implementation of IFRS. Moreover, these secondary resources have also not detailed the changes that the IFRS will undergo during the post BREXIT situation.

2.6 Summary

This section has provided a critical analysis of the findings presented in other secondary resources such as articles, journals and books. Moreover, this section has highlighted the issues associated with IFRS reporting, the financial implications of these standards and the role of IASB in developing and monitoring these standards. Lastly, this section has also mentioned the gaps that have not been fulfilled by the existing literature.

3: Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The research methodology is considered to be the most important chapter that helps the researcher to recognise the process of collecting information with appropriate classification and interpretation of the collected data. The portion of methodology helps the researcher to assess the overall reliability and validity of the study. The research methodology involves all the techniques and methods with appropriate applications of research approach, philosophy, design, sample size and techniques, data analysis, ethical consideration and data collection. In this research work, the researcher will use all these methods in order to collect appropriate information. Therefore, the researcher will conduct the survey process including the interview process to collect the realistic information from the appropriate sources.

3.2 Research outline

Research outline is considered as the primary step utilised by the researcher in order to develop a structure with the proper planning regarding the collection of information using appropriate methods and processes. Therefore, the research outline mainly allows the researcher to organise the overall research work in an appropriate order.

Figure 3.1: Research Onion

The research outline helps the researcher in the form of a map to conduct all the processes for collecting information based on the structure. Consequently, the research outline helps to develop appropriate concepts regarding all the methods while using the techniques of collecting information. For this particular study, the researcher has used the positivism philosophy, deductive approach and descriptive design in order to collect and real information for conducting the overall study for making the research work more effective.

3.3 Research Philosophy

Orngreen and Levinsen (2017) stated that the research philosophy is mainly corresponding to the advancement of appropriate information and skills including the essence. The research philosophy mainly represents the viewpoint of the researcher based on the strategy regarding the study. On the other hand, the research philosophy is referred to as the trust and belief regarding the process of collecting the information, which can easily be analysed and obtained after using it properly. The research philosophy is classified in three sections: positivism, realism and interpretivism.

Figure 3.2: Research Philosophy

For this particular research work, the researcher has used positivism philosophy in order to interpret the collected information in a critical way. Therefore, the positivism philosophy helps in confirming the trust regarding the reliability based on truthful information that has been collected using the methods in an appropriate way. Apart from this, the positivism philosophy helps to analyse all the information in an analytical process. The researcher used the positivism philosophy for collecting both reliable and accurate information on the basis of the research topic. On the other hand, positivism philosophy also helps the researcher to make the research study more authentic using the analytical methodology for enabling them to perform more accurately in detail. However, the use of this particular method helps the researcher to use the benefits after the formation of hypotheses for quantifying the result of the study.

3.4 Research Approach

The research approach is another important method, which the researcher has selected to use for recognising the appropriate method for collecting information following the developed plants in a

detailed way. It involves different interpretations based on the analysis regarding the purpose of Data Collection. On the other hand, the research approach also helps the researcher to select suitable tools that are required to highlight the research problems (Mohajan, 2018). The research approach accommodates various stages based on the methods that involve appropriate analysis for better interpretation of the methods of data collection. Therefore, all the factors are significant for addressing and identifying the basic nature of the research problem that involves suitable reasoning on the basis of their analysis. The incorporated factors are very significant for completing the overall research work in a better way.

Figure 3.3: Research Approach

The research approaches are of two types: the inductive approach and the deductive approach. The inductive approaches are mainly used by the researcher in order to develop and use the appropriate new theories and models. The inductive approach is mainly used for highlighting the concept regarding the themes and models broadly in order to analyse the qualitative data (Zangirolami-Raimundo et al., 2018). On the other hand, the deductive approach usually deals with the basic theories for making the study more realistic and effective. This also validates the accurate and appropriate reasons regarding the effect and impact of organisation culture based on innovation management.

For this particular research work, the researcher has used a deductive approach. The topic is mainly based on the logical reasons for the appropriate conclusion. It also involves some analysis based on qualitative data analysis procedure in order to test the hypothesis using the methods to correlated factors. Therefore, it mainly helps to highlight the concept for providing the difference between the original and variable factors regarding the deduction process of the hypothesis. Apart from this, it also deals with the basic hypothesis with relevant methods for reaching the logical conclusion.

3.5 Research Design

The research design is the methods of conducting the study where the researcher needs to identify the structure of the whole dissertation. The research design is the overall strategy to prepare the whole research. Here the researcher makes the strategic plan for the study with a short and logical plan to establish the research question by collecting and data, analysing it and interpreting the analysing (Attia and Edge, 2017). There are three types of research design. These are explanatory, explanatory and descriptive designs. The explanatory design is defined as the design where the researcher has to take the explanatory ways where the research topic has no such information from other secondary sources. On the other hand, the exploratory design is defined as the research strategy, which has to explore the whole topic as there is no such information or research done previously the researcher has to rely on his or her own capabilities of exploring the whole study (Ngozwana, 2018). The last one is the conduction of research by the descriptive research design where the researcher can take data and information from different sources and can interpret the data through proper analysis.

Figure 3.4: Research Design

In this research, the descriptive research design has been taken under consideration as the researcher will take up different secondary sources to collect data. The data and information are being analysed through different theoretical perception and interpreted through discussion. The research will be conducted by the researcher by descriptive design strategy. Here the researcher will make the plan of study by taking up the data and information from the research papers done on the related topic previously and describe it through theoretical underpinning.

3.6 Data Collection Method

The data collection method is the practically first practical part of the research. Here the researcher has to identify from where the research data and information has to be collected. There are many sources, which can be considered for collecting data. Researchers can use the internet to find out different journals, articles, blogs, or any other resources as well as they can also conduct surveys and interview processes to interact with people directly and ask questions related to the topic.

The main aim of this part of methodology is to understand which data collection can be used for a particular study (Basias and Pollalis, 2018). The data collection methods are of two types, which are the primary data collection and secondary data collection methods. In primary data collection methods, I have gathered required data and information through conducting online surveys (by using SurveyMonkey). In this case, I have just created a form (by putting all of the questionnaires) and shared it to the target respondents so that they can fillip the forms from their home. Moreover, in the present research study, I have taken the secondary data collection into my consideration as well. Through the secondary data collection, I have made the Literature review, as all of the given data and information are taken from online sources, like books, journals, newspapers and websites (which are secondary sources). Therefore, it can be said that I have considered primary and secondary data collection method, as a Mixed Approach for this research study.

In addition, I have shared the survey form with 125 people who are directly in the financial marketing and core sector. Among the 125, I got response from 70 respondents. On the other hand, I have applied Random Probability Sampling technique for sharing the survey form among the chosen target audiences.

3.7 Data Analysis

The data analysis is the process where the researcher needs to analyse, interpret the data, and analyse it based on the understandings. The researcher has to understand which data needs which methods of data analysis. The analysis is being based on the requirements, aims, and objectives of the research paper (Clarke and Visser, 2019). The problem statement defines the way of the analysis and the requirements. The data analysis methods can be divided into two types, which are the quantitative and qualitative research analysis. Qualitative analysis needs to be conducted where the data and information is not involved with any numerical values. The statistics and data is not involved in qualitative analysis. The researcher has to make analysis from the perceptions of data and information from different sources (Cuervo-Cazurra et al., 2017). The quantitative data analysis is based on numerical data and statistics. The quantitative analysis is based on the data and information gathered from the survey process. In this research study, the researcher uses both quantitative secondary thematic analyses. The research has conducted the quantitative data analysis process over the data, which is gathered through online surveys. The quantitative analysis has taken the numbers and statistics gathered from the survey process to

conduct the analytical discussion, as it helps to find out a suitable outcome for this entire research study based on perceptions of the chosen respondents. In order to analyse the numerical data of quantitative analysis, I have taken Statistical approaches like Descriptive statistics, Regression, T-test, Chi-square methods for testing the research hypothesis.

3.8 Ethical Consideration

While conducting the research work it is required for the researcher to follow all the ethical consideration in an appropriate way. The researcher has followed the ethical guidelines of UoC for conducting this particular study in order to maintain, analyse and complete every chapter of this work. On the other hand, the researcher has followed the validation, confidentiality, privacy and reliability in order to achieve the criteria that are needed to complete the research work. Moreover, the Data Protection Act 2018 has also been used for protecting all the information that has been collected relevant to the research topic. The research has also maintained all the political and legal aspects in order to conduct in both the survey and interview process for conducting both the primary data collection method and secondary data collection method with appropriate restrictions. Including all these, the researcher has also followed the integrity availability in order to maintain the continuation of the research regarding the using the resources for collecting information with appropriate plans.

3.9 Timeline

Activities	Duration
Selection of research topic	week 1
Set research objectives and questions	week 2 & 3
Implemented a critical review of the literature	week 4 & 5
Analysing the literature gaps in research	week 6
Making proper strategies for gathering data	week 7
Analysing the findings of the research	week 8 & 9
The collected data tested and validated	week 10
Delivering the report	week 11 & 12

Table 3.1: Research Timeline

(Source: Self-created)

3.10 Summary

In this research work, the researcher has used and highlighted all the methods to conduct the study in an appropriate and effective way. However, the researcher has used a different philosophy approach and design following the positivism philosophy, deductive approach and descriptive design for collecting information relevant to the research topic. For collecting information, the researcher has also used both the survey and interview process in order to collect the realistic information regarding the research topic. On the other hand, the research timeline has also been highlighted.

Chapter 4: Result and Analysis

4.1 Introduction

This specific section implies the data analysis procedures through which I will draw the outcome of this entire research paper. In this section, I have used quantitative data analysis (through table and graphs), descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and hypothesis testing through t-Test.

4.2 Quantitative Analysis

Q1. What is your age?

Responses	Rating on the basis of responses	Number of responses	Percentage (%)	Total number of respondents
Less than 30 years	1	26	37.1428571	70
30 – 50 years	2	25	35.7142857	70
Above than 50 years	3	19	27.1428571	70

Table 4.2.1: Age

Figure 4.2.1: Age

Analysis

The above survey table highlights the age of the respondents. Therefore, 37% of the respondents are less than 30 years and 35% of the respondents are in between the age group of 30 to 50 years. On the other hand, 27% of the respondents are from the age group who are above 50 years.

Q2. What is your gender?

Responses	Rating on the basis of responses	Number of responses	Percentage (%)	Total number of respondents
Male	1	36	51.4285714	70
Female	2	33	47.1428571	70
Rather not to say	3	1	1.42857143	70

Table 4.2.2: Gender

Figure 4.2.2: Gender

Analysis

This table shows the gender of the respondents that have participated in this survey process. It shows the 51% of the male respondents among 70 respondents. On the other hand, there were 47% of women respondents and 1% from others.

Q3. How long have you been working in this financial sector?

Responses	Rating on the basis of responses	Number of responses	Percentage (%)	Total number of respondents
Less than 2 years	1	19	27.1428571	70
2 – 5 years	2	24	34.2857143	70
More than 5 years	3	27	38.5714286	70

Figure 4.2.3: Working Experience

Analysis

The survey table highlights the number of years the respondents have worked or still working. Among 70 respondents, 27% of the respondents worked in this financial sector for less than 2 years. Apart from that, 34% of the respondents are working for 2 to 5 years and the rest 38% of the respondents are working for more than 5 years.

Q4. What is the type of your working firm affiliation?

Responses	Rating on the basis of responses	Number of responses	Percentage (%)	Total number of respondents
Small	1	22	31.4285714	70
Regional	2	23	32.8571429	70
Multinational	3	25	35.7142857	70

Figure 4.2.4: Working firm affiliation

Analysis

From the above survey table, the type of working firm affiliation can be understood. Among 70 respondents, 31% of the respondents supported the option of small firm affiliation. Whereas, 32% of the respondents have supported the option of regional firm affiliation and 35% of the respondents have selected the multinational firm as their affiliation.

Q5. How far do you believe that every financial organization needs to adopt the IFRS method?

Responses	Rating on the basis of responses	Number of responses	Percentage (%)	Total number of respondents
Strongly Agree	1	23	32.8571429	70
Agree	2	19	27.1428571	70
Neutral	3	4	5.71428571	70
Disagree	4	18	25.7142857	70
Strongly Disagree	5	6	8.57142857	70

Table 4.2.5: Perception on the needs to adopt the IFRS method

Figure 4.2.5: Perception on the needs to adopt the IFRS method

Analysis

This above survey table shows the requirement of the financial organization for the adoption of the IFRS methods. Among 70 respondents, 32% of the respondents have strongly agreed with it and 27% of the respondents have agreed with it. The IFRS is required as it is an international standard of accounting that highlights the appropriate kind of transactions based on the financial statements. On the other hand, 5% of the respondents gave neutral responses among 70 respondents. 25% of them have disagreed with and 8% have strongly disagreed with it.

Q6. Do you believe that the IFRS method is best for ensuring quality?

Responses	Rating on the basis of responses	Number of responses	Percentage (%)	Total number of respondents
Yes	1	47	67.1428571	70
No	2	15	21.4285714	70
Rather not to say	3	8	11.4285714	70

Table 4.2.6: Perception on IFRS method for ensuring quality

(Source: Refer to Excel)

Figure 4.2.6: Perception on IFRS method for ensuring quality

Analysis

The above survey table shows the IFRS method is best for ensuring quality. Among 70 respondents, 67% of the respondents have supported the option of Yes and 21 % of the respondents have supported the option of No. IFRS method is best for ensuring quality because it is beneficial for the economy by developing the growth of the business internationally. Proper quality also helps to encourage the investors for investing for the flow of the foreign capitals in the country.

Q7. How far do you believe that everyone working in the financial sector should have proper perceptions about the relation of legal System factors to the UK's IFRS adoption and application?

Responses	Rating on the basis of responses	Number of responses	Percentage (%)	Total number of respondents
Strongly Agree	1	28	40	70
Agree	2	8	11.4285714	70
Neutral	3	4	5.71428571	70
Disagree	4	20	28.5714286	70
Strongly Disagree	5	10	14.2857143	70

Table 4.2.7: Perception on the relation of legal System factors to the UK's IFRS adoption and application

Figure 4.2.7: Perception on the relation of legal System factors to the UK's IFRS adoption and application

Analysis

Based on the survey table, this can be understood that those who are working in the financial sector should have proper perceptions about the relation of legal System factors to the UK's IFRS adoption and application. Among 70 respondents, 40% of the respondents have strongly agreed with it and 11% of the respondents have agreed with it. The maintenance of IFRS is important and every organisation should have the capability of adapting such rules and regulations. Other than this, 4% of the respondents gave neutral responses among 70 respondents. 20% of them have disagreed with and 10% have strongly disagreed with it.

Q8. How far do you believe that everyone working in the financial sector should have proper perceptions about the relation of the Taxation System Factor to the UK's IFRS adoption and application?

Responses	Rating on the basis of responses	Number of responses	Percentage (%)	Total number of respondents
Strongly Agree	1	28	40	70
Agree	2	8	11.4285714	70

Neutral	3	4	5.71428571	70
Disagree	4	21	30	70
Strongly Disagree	5	9	12.8571429	70

Table 4.2.8: Perceptions on the relation of the Taxation System Factor to the UK's IFRS adoption and application

Figure 4.2.8: Perceptions on the relation of the Taxation System Factor to the UK's IFRS adoption and application

Analysis

Based on the survey table, this can be understood that those who are working in the financial sector should have proper perceptions about the relation of the Taxation System Factor to the UK's IFRS adoption and application. Among 70 respondents, 40% of the respondents have strongly agreed with it and 11% of the respondents have agreed with it. The taxation system is important because it helps in visa applications, loan approval, government tenders, high-cover life insurance and others. Other than this, 4% of the respondents gave neutral responses among 70 respondents. 20% of them have disagreed with and 10% have strongly disagreed with it.

Q9. How far do you believe that economic and political ties factors should have a healthy relation with IFRS adoption and application of the UK's financial sector?

Responses	Rating on the basis of responses	Number of responses	Percentage (%)	Total number of respondents
Strongly Agree	1	20	28.5714286	70
Agree	2	23	32.8571429	70
Neutral	3	6	8.57142857	70
Disagree	4	14	20	70
Strongly Disagree	5	7	10	70

Table 4.2.9: Perception on the relation of economic and political ties factors with IFRS adoption and application of the UK's financial sector

Figure 4.2.9: Perception on the relation of economic and political ties factors with IFRS adoption and application of the UK's financial sector

From the survey table, this can be observed that economic and political ties factors should have a healthy relation with IFRS adoption and application of the UK's financial sector. Among 70 respondents, 28% of the respondents have strongly agreed with it and 32% of the respondents have agreed with it. The economic and political situation in the UK is quite different from other countries. The financial standards are also different. The relationship between economy and politics always becomes the most important factor in the maintenance of the finance statements. The economic and political ties factor

have a healthy relation with IFRS adaptation. Other than this, 8% of the respondents gave neutral responses among 70 respondents. 20% of them have disagreed with and 10% have strongly disagreed with it.

Q 10. Do you believe that the cultural structure of the UK is dependent on the application and adaptation of the IFRS method?

Responses	Rating on the basis of responses	Number of responses	Percentage (%)	Total number of respondents
Yes	1	35	50	70
No	2	26	37.1428571	70
Rather not to say	3	9	12.8571429	70

Table 4.2.10: Perception over the dependency of cultural structure on the application and adaptation of the IFRS method

Figure 4.2.10: Perception over the dependency of cultural structure on the application and adaptation of the IFRS method

Analysis

The above survey table shows the cultural structure of the UK is dependent on the application and adaptation of the IFRS method. Among 70 respondents, 50% of the respondents have supported the

option of Yes and 37 % of the respondents have supported the option of No. Lastly, 12% of the respondents supported the section of rather not say.

Q11. What are the issues and complications that an organization can face while adapting and implementing IFRS?

Responses	Rating on the basis of responses	Number of responses	Percentage (%)	Total number of respondents
Transition problems	1	23	32.86	70
Lack of expertise	2	16	22.86	70
Time consuming	3	12	17.14	70
Costly than others	4	19	27.14	70

Table 11: Issues and complications that an organization can face while adapting and implementing IFRS

Figure 11: The issues and complications that an organization can face while adapting and implementing IFRS

Analysis

From the survey table, this can be observed that the issues and complications that an organization can face while adapting and implementing IFRS. Among 70 respondents, 32% of the respondents have supported the transition problems and 22% of the respondents have supported the lack of expertise. Other than this, 17% of the respondents have supported time consuming among 70 respondents. 27% of them have disagreed with and 10% have supported costly than others.

4.3 Descriptive Analysis

4.3.1 Mean

Serial Number	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11
Mean	2.1142	2.04286	2.5	1.44286	2.65714	2.64286	2.5	1.6285	2.38
	9							7	57

4.3.2 Median

Serial Number	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11
Median	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1.5	2

4.3.3 Mode

Serial Number	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11
Mode	3	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	1

4.3.4 Standard Deviation

Serial Number	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11
SD	0.80834	0.82419	1.40135	0.6944	1.5778	1.56071	1.35935	0.70549	1.2074

4.3.5 Regression Analysis

Survey question 1 and question 2 are not taken into consideration for this analysis, as both of these two questions are demographic and generalized questions. The following table highlights the choice of variables for this analysis -

Work experience	Dependent Variable / Intercept
Perception on working firm affiliation	Independent Variable
Perception on the need of adaptation of IFRS method	Independent Variable
Perception on IFRS as a quality maintaining method	Independent Variable
Relation among legal system and IFRS method	Independent Variable
Relation among Taxation system and IFRS method	Independent Variable
Relation among political and economic ties factors and IFRS method	Independent Variable
Relation among cultural structure and IFRS method	Independent Variable
Issues faced by organizations while implementing and adopting IFRS	Independent Variable

Table 4.3.5.1: Research Variable identification

(Source: Self-created)

Multiple Regressions

SUMMARY OUTPUT

Regression Statistics	
	0.517555
Multiple R	0.931
	0.267864
R Square	0.141
Adjusted R Square	0.183848
Standard Error	0.735506
Observations	69

ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	7	12.0733	1.724757	3.188267	0.00609
Residual	61	32.99917	0.54097		
Total	68	45.07246			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	2.683808		5.850	2.08E-07	3.6010	1.766525	1.76652	3.60109
3	0.162694		1.312	0.194		0.0851		0.08517
1	0.061062	0.101359	0.602	0.549	-0.41057	0.1416	-0.41057	0.14161

The Practical implications to all organizations implementing the IFRS in the UK

	021		43					
	-		-					
	0.196217		1.408	0.164		0.0823		0.08235
2	351	0.139314	45	074	-0.47479	59	-0.47479	9
	-		-					
	1.668204		2.171	0.033				
1	271	0.768249	44	797	-3.20441	-0.132	-3.20441	-0.132
	1.821490		2.365	0.021		3.3611	0.28184	3.36113
1	96	0.769966	676	191	0.281848	34	8	4
	0.101807		1.230	0.223		0.2672		0.26722
2	284	0.082724	692	163	-0.06361	23	-0.06361	3
	-		-					
	0.269950		1.938	0.057		0.0084		0.00846
1	687	0.139233	84	151	-0.54836	63	-0.54836	3

4.4 Hypothesis Testing

Here, I am performing T-test in order to test the chosen hypotheses based on the following conditions –

If t Stat is larger than t Critical Two-tail, then we reject the null hypothesis

If t Stat is smaller than t Critical Two-tail, then we reject the alternative hypothesis

T-test on Q3 and Q4

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	2	3
Mean	2.115942	2.028986
Variance	0.66283	0.675618

The Practical implications to all organizations implementing the IFRS in the UK

Observations	69	69
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	136	
t Stat	0.624347	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.266723	
t Critical one-tail	1.656135	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.533446	
t Critical two-tail	1.977561	

From the above table, it can be identified that t Stat value is 0.624347, whereas t Critical Two-tail is standing on 1.977561, which is far larger than t Stat. Therefore, for this case, it can be said that H0 is satisfied.

T-test on Q3 and Q5

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	2	1
Mean	2.115942	2.521739

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Variance	0.66283	1.959079
Observations	69	69
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	109	
t Stat	-2.08173	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.019854	
t Critical one-tail	1.658953	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.039709	
t Critical two-tail	1.981967	

The above table highlights that t Critical two-tail value 1.981967 is larger than t stat, which is (-)2.08173. Therefore, it implies that H₀, the null hypothesis is satisfied here.

T-test on Q3 and Q6

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

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	2	2
Mean	2.115942	1.434783
Variance	0.66283	0.484655
Observations	69	69
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	133	
t Stat	5.282017	
P(T<=t) one-tail	2.54E-07	
t Critical one-tail	1.656391	
P(T<=t) two-tail	5.08E-07	
t Critical two-tail	1.977961	

The above T test depicts that H1 is satisfied here, as t stat value (5.282017) is larger than t Critical two-tail value 1.977961. That is why, H0 is rejected here.

T-test on Q3 and Q7

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

The Practical implications to all organizations implementing the IFRS in the UK

	2	1
Mean	2.115942	2.681159
Variance	0.66283	2.485081
Observations	69	69
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	102	
t Stat	-2.64624	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.004714	
t Critical one-tail	1.65993	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.009429	
t Critical two-tail	1.983495	

In this scenario, H0 is satisfied, as t Critical two-tail value (1.983495) stands larger than t Stat value, which is (-)2.64624.

T-test on Q3 and Q8

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

The Practical implications to all organizations implementing the IFRS in the UK

	2	1
Mean	2.115942	2.666667
Variance	0.66283	2.431373
Observations	69	69
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	103	
t Stat	-2.60067	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.005336	
t Critical one-tail	1.659782	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.010672	
t Critical two-tail	1.983264	

In this case, the null hypothesis (H0) is also satisfied, as the value of t Stat (-)2.60067 is smaller than the value of t Critical two-tail that is 1.983264.

T-test on Q3 and Q9

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

The Practical implications to all organizations implementing the IFRS in the UK

	2	2
Mean	2.115942	2.507246
Variance	0.66283	1.87127
Observations	69	69
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	111	
t Stat	-2.04187	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.021768	
t Critical one-tail	1.658697	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.043535	
t Critical two-tail	1.981567	

Null Hypothesis (H0) is accepted here instead of H1 (Alternative hypothesis), as the value of t Stat is (-2.04187, which is smaller than the value of t Critical two-tail 1.981567.

T-test on Q3 and Q10

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

The Practical implications to all organizations implementing the IFRS in the UK

	2	1
Mean	2.115942	1.637681
Variance	0.66283	0.499147
Observations	69	69
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	133	
t Stat	3.68545	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.000166	
t Critical one-tail	1.656391	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.000331	
t Critical two-tail	1.977961	

The Alternative Hypothesis (H1) is satisfied in this case, as t Critical two-tail value (1.977961) stands smaller than t Stat value (3.68545), which is why H0 is rejected.

4.5 Summary of result

The entire hypothesis testing majorly highlights the satisfaction of H0 (Null Hypothesis) instead of H1 (Alternative Hypothesis). This implies that the IFRS standards are complicated, and organizations face different issues while implementing this standard. The following section will discuss this outcome of the dissertation with the help of related literature.

Chapter 5: Discussion of Results

Extent of knowledge regarding IFRS

This research has highlighted that IFRS standards are essential for improving the financial position of the organisation. These accounting standards also help in auditing services as auditors can use this as a basis of examining the financial statements. However, for preparing accounting information and financial statements, the organizations need to possess an in-depth knowledge regarding the concept, frameworks and the application principles of the accounting standards like IAS, IFRS and GAAP. Due to this reason, the majority of the respondents that have taken part in the survey have more than 5 years of experience in the accounting field. These respondents have witnessed several changes to both the IAS and IFRS. These individuals have been able to utilise these accounting standards and principles and these respondents have faced huge problems while transitioning to the changed accounting principles and frameworks. Furthermore, IFRS and IAS are to be applied by all registered companies irrespective of their size. Moreover, it has also been found that large, medium as well as small companies implement these accounting principles to benchmark their financial performance with other competitors in the market.

Adoption of IFRS

In case of the overall adoption of IFRS, only companies that are registered in the UK regulated markets. Companies that are registered in London Stock Exchange, ICE Futures Europe, AQSE main Market, International Property Securities should follow the IFRS principles. However, the majority of these organizations have faced huge difficulties to implement IFRS standards. These companies have faced huge difficulties managing the endorsement provisions related to IFRS. It has been found that there are huge discrepancies in the way IFRS standards are practiced and implemented in different companies throughout the UK. Moreover, there are also various companies within the UK which follow the GAAP principles. Due to this reason, it has become difficult to compare the financial statements of these

organizations due to the increased gaps between these accounting practices. The accounting boards have implemented "Simpler Financial Reporting for Micro Entities, small companies, limited liability partnerships' for effective management of the accounting practices set by the accounting boards". Sometimes it becomes difficult for the companies to properly implement each of these elements to match the accounting principles with separate accounting information and records.

Implementation of IFRS and its implication

The Accounting standards have been implemented with the objective of maintaining the accounting and financial records at a similar structure. It is important for the companies to compare their financial position with the competitors. Therefore, as the competition is not only domestic, but also international, the record of the financial statements should be maintained at a similar standard. Here IFRS has made the job easy and every company who has its operational base in the international market should follow the IFRS rules and regulations. As per the survey process, it has been clearly indicated that the IFRS rules and regulations for maintaining financial records are helpful and easy to understand. I, as a researcher, have to deal with many rules and regulations that IFRS has implemented In the financial record keeping activities. I think that though some of the rules and regulations are for the ease of understanding the financial statement; there are certain issues that have been generated. Therefore, I thought of asking people about their perceptions regarding the difficulties that I had faced earlier while dealing with the rules and regulations of IFRS. In the survey, I listed some of the issues like the transition problems, lack of expertise, time consumption and cost inefficacy.

Transition of IFRS

As per the outcome of the survey I had seen that most of the people think that the transition of the accounting structure from the local GAAP to the IFRS rules is the most problematic feature. However, I can agree to this point. From my experience, I have seen that when a company starts to follow the domestic GAAP for recording the financial statements, it becomes habituated and when it has to be translated into IFRS, the change is really major. Many considerations have to be kept in kind and or else, serious mistakes or flaws can be generated. The company needs to understand the local GAAP is not for international use. In the international market companies use different formats which help them to make the comparison and can evaluate the financial situation. However, due to habituation, the translation of the financial statement into the IFRS has to be said to be one of the major issues or drawbacks that has to be faced.

On the other hand, it has also been seen that people having thorough knowledge about IFRS is very little. It is obvious that from the educational level to the professional level, industry prioritizes the maintenance of the local GAAP. This basically increases the problem of not knowing the IFRS rules. Consequently, when the transformation happens, due to lack of expatriation, the translation of accounting records become ineffective and mistakes can be seen in a huge number. Hence, apart from the transition problem, another issue of IFRS is the lack of expertise.

Requirements for adopting to IFRS

As a researcher, I think that any standard, which is for the ease of maintenance is important, and every organisation should have the capability of adapting such rules and regulations. I had a question in my mind whether the UK is dependent on the application and adaptation of the IFRS methods or not. Thus I asked this question to the participants of the survey. It was quite expected that 50% of the participants think that the cultural structure of the UK is adaptive and they can be suitable for using IFRS. However, my conception was not different. As UK GAAP is not very different from the rules and regulations of IFRS, the transition of accounting statements will not be difficult. The structure of recording the financial activities and transactions are more or less same for UK GAAP compared to that of IFRS.

The progressive culture of the UK helps their organizations to understand the importance of maintaining their financial statements as per the guidelines of IFRS. This helps them to increase the opportunities of having the benefits of easy comparison of the financial position of the multi-national organizations of the UK. The focus of the UK organization is to have a fair competition in the international market. Therefore, in order to make the comparison fair and understandable, their accounting standards mainly focused on the main requirements of the IFRS, though they have their own standards. This, as a result, helps in comparison and fulfilling the international standards. Therefore, the transition becomes smooth and easy to understand.

Challenges of adopting to IFRS and other accounting policies

37% of the participants think that the UK's cultural structure is not capable of adapting to the IFRS. I can say that they have their point as the UK's accounting standards are not flexible. The financial statement structure is not being prepared in such a way that they can change the structure with much flexibility. This may cause difficulties in the transition period. As a result, it has been said that the financial statements may not be easy to understand. The issue in the UK GAAP is that the lack of flexibility in the financial structure does not allow for easy understanding and transition of the records into IFRS. Therefore, in the time of comparison it becomes difficult for the organization to comprehend the financial position of the company compared to that of the competitors.

The economic and political situation in the UK is quite different from other countries. The financial standards are also different. The relationship between economy and politics always becomes the most important factor in the maintenance of the finance statements. Organizations have to cope up with regular changing standards. The financial sector of the UK has been seen to be in different difficulties in adopting IFRS rules and regulations for the maintenance of the financial statements. Though the economic and political ties factor have a healthy relation with IFRS adaptation. The application in the UK financial sector is quite difficult. However according to my survey report I have seen that more than 60% participants think that the relationship between economic and political factors have a huge influence in the financial sector of UK and adaptation of the IFRS is becoming more easier with this ties factor. The accounting institutes, which are being controlled by the government of the UK, has different structure of maintaining financial records. According to the local standards of financial activities, GAAP has been formulated by the financial accounting standard board of the UK. This standard is mostly followed by the organizations in England and helps in the promotion and implementation of the standard driven processes.

Economic consequences of IFRS

The economic position of the country is being comprehended by the financial records of the organization, which are being recorded as per the GAAP. However, it has been seen that the organizations that have both the standards in their financial activities have different outcomes of their financial position. It has been seen that in majority cases the value relevance of forecasted earnings has reduced under the IFRS system. Even though I have seen that according to my survey maximum people think that the UK financial Sector has the capability of adapting IFRS and the transition will not be very difficult. I think that due to less flexibility in the financial standards the transition of the financial activities from GAAP to IFRS Will makes it more complex and difficult to make comparisons.

Differences between GAAP vs IFRS

Oftentimes it becomes difficult for the companies to properly implement each of these elements to match the accounting principles with separate accounting information and records. There are also huge levels of discrepancies between the GAAP principles and IFRS policies. It has been seen that as per the GAAP principles, revenues should be recognized when it is realized and earned and not when it has been received. On the other hand, expenses should be recognized when the payment has been actually incurred. However, these principles differ to a large extent in case of the IFRS principles. In this case, revenues should be recognized based on a reasonable measurement. According to IFRS, there are several conditions that have to be fulfilled for revenue recognition. These conditions are:

- The costs of the revenue have been measured on reasonable terms

- The revenue are possible to be measured on some reasonable criteria
- The seller does not have any control over the goods that have been sold

Thus, it can be understood that the IFRS standard is mostly based on theoretical concepts and qualitative concepts that are highly relevant. This creates huge difficulties for the companies that practice the GAAP principles and IFRS principles. Similarly in the case of asset recognition and valuation, both IFRS and GAAP recommend different policies. It has been seen that as per GAAP, an asset needs to have 3 essential characteristics, namely: embodiment of a profitable future benefit, ability to generate future net cash flows and proper access. On the other hand, the IFRS principles only recognise a property as an asset when it has some future economic benefits. Moreover, the cost of the asset needs to be measured on a reasonable basis. In this context, it has to be mentioned that ifrs method is better suited for ensuring quality as well as comparability between the accounts.

Model of IFRS

As per the rules and regulations of FRS it has been said that the companies who are operating internationally should have how standardised financial statements. It has been seen that companies have branches in different countries where they have to maintain different standards for maintaining their financial records. Hence IFRS have provided standardised guidelines where every organization operating in the international market has the opportunity to have a single financial statement which is easy to understand and comparable. By saying models of IFRS it means that the consolidated income statement, consolidated balance sheet, Consolidated cash flow statement, consolidated statement of changes in equity, consolidated statement of financial position and independent auditors report. In these models the organizations who are operating in the global market have the opportunity to have a single financial statement record where they can understand their financial position easily and can compare it With other competitors.

The term consolidated means together, means the organizations can take all the transacted amounts under one single currency and standards to record in the financial statements. The profit and loss statement shows the profit or loss of the company for a period. In this statement, the organization can record all the incomes earned and expenditure incurred from all branches in different countries for a financial year. By deducting the expenditure, both direct and indirect, from the income, both direct and indirect, the profit or loss can be determined. The profit and loss statement under IFRS starts from recording the revenue income and then subtracting the cost of sales the gross profit can be calculated. Next the operating profit is calculated by deducting the operating expenses from the gross profit. Then the Profit before tax from the indirect expenses and followed by the profit after tax, which is the net profit of the company.

After the profit and loss statement, the company has to prepare the financial statement which is the balance sheet of the company. This records the assets and liabilities including the share capital of the company for the particular period. This statement followed by the statement of changes in equity. This statement includes the profit or loss of the organization and applying a retrospective effect, the errors in equity are being checked. This shows the actual amount of equity share capital the organization has for that period of time.

This will be followed by the cash flow statement. In this statement the company recorded all the cash or cash equivalent transactions which every branch of the company has gone through in every market for the period. The most important feature of this statement is that only cash and cash equivalent transactions will be considered. Three main parts have to be prepared to show the cash transaction. These are the cash flow from operating activities, cash flow from investment activities and cash flow from financial activities. In each of the activities, there is cash inflow and cash outflow. The cash inflow shows the income generation of the company whereas the cash outflow shows the expenditures. In each of the activities the cash inflow and outflow determines the ultimate cash and cash equivalent balance of the company. This may vary with the balance shown in the consolidated financial position statement or balance sheet. Lastly, the independent auditor's report shows the reflection of the auditor to declare all the financial statements to be at the best of truth and ethical considerations. With the consent of the auditor in the report, the company can get the certification of their authentication of their ethical considerations.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendation

6.1 Conclusion

With the help of the EC regulation 1606/2002 (the IAS Regulation), the International Financial Reporting Standards has become a part of the United Kingdom from the year 2005. The IAS Regulation made the UK companies build up proper securities for trading in accordance with regulations in the market. Now, in the previous chapters, there are various themes explained according to the objectives and the aims. It has helped to reach and satisfy the need of the dissertation topic. In this section of the dissertation, we have to conduct an overview by linking up the themes and objectives with the effective quantitative analysis. By this means, it will help me to reach the core of the research. Identification of the research objective helped me to research the secondary data provided by the previous researchers. However, the secondary analysis, which is represented in the second chapter, helped a lot to understand the features, challenges, advantages, and disadvantages of the IFRS Standards. Before recognizing the accounting standards in the UK means, I have cleared that various fraudulent activities happen regularly in the companies. It cannot always be seen by the managers or the team leaders, hence, to understand and

identify every company keeps their accounting records with them. A financial expert and audit expert tries to solve the fraudulent activities and the error activities that arise in any kind of business. The necessity of the IFRS Standards needs to be clear that it is implemented to build more transparency between the company employees and the hierarchy. With the laws that are served in the IFRS Standards, the companies are bound to keep proper records for their financial activities. The activities are recorded at the end of every day so that they can get a proper review at the end of every month. This continuous expertise report for the financial activities, the management gets a proper overview about their financial performance, which helps them to calculate their financial profit or loss at the end of the year.

6.2 Linking with objective

6.2.1 Objective 1: To identify the issues that can arise while implementing the IFRS standards

This first objective stated that identification of the issues at the time of implementing the IFRS Standards causes various problems because there is a lot of jurisdiction, which is hard to follow by the companies at a time. Among the private, public, and volunteer companies in the countries like India, Australia, Russia, Kenya, South Africa, and many others, all the identified Public limited companies need to gather capital from the shareholders to continue the business in the market. In this case, many shareholders look into the financial statements of the companies, which affect the public companies to convince them for a better opportunity. Hence, for conducting more relevant and proper statements regarding the company financial condition accounting standards are being applied. It also helps them control fraudulent activities and gain the trust of the shareholders for more investment. It can be seen that by implementing the IFRS standards they are gaining more profit at the end of the year.

According to theme 1 in the second chapter, the basic observation is considered that the accounting principles can solve the problems regarding control of the fraudulent activities and error of the production lists. The firms like the retail stores, banking sector, and the other companies under the Public sector should refer to the accounting standards that review with monitoring the cost constraints. According to the research procedures, a large amount of quantitative analysis comes up in the front for the accountants of the company. By solving the entire costing of the company, the project gets implemented, which is stated to be one of the best procedures to maintain the budgetary means and the profit ratio of the company at the end of the year.

6.2.2 Objective 2: To implement the effects of IFRS on the profitability and equity position of the organization

Based on the current situation of the companies of the UK, it has been seen that there are various companies, who are hiring a team of accounts and who have the only duty to solve the cost-cutting system of the company and control the entire budget at the time of production. With the help of the theories provided in chapter, two stated about two kinds of regulation that affected the companies and

conducted by the government of the UK. These two regulations started interfering with the companies' financial statements to hold up the wealth of the country. According to the rules and regulations conducted by the IFRS, it was seen that the companies were facing certain issues by increasing complexity, dynamic, and the changing rules of the implementation of laws. Hence, in this situation, it went towards the UK GAAP analysis, where the businesses were required to provide various documents to justify their business investments. These implementations of the law and rules helped the firms to keep more transparency at the time of work. In addition, the quantitative analysis stated a positive result, because this causes a better result towards the costing and the other financial approaches.

6.2.3 Objective 3: To determine the role-played by accounting institutes in formulating these standards

In accordance with theme 2 from the chapter literature review, it can be seen that the objective is well described. There are various institutes where the accounting formulas are formulated by the researchers or the scientists, by the help of those institutes the companies get a proper way to identify and conduct a way out to improve and purify from fraudulent activities. In case of these, the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) has 22 founders who help to make the body independent in this situation. The identified objective was entirely justified with the help of this theme as it defines and mentions various ways, which can lead the organizations more efficiently at the time of their presentations. Emerging with new theories and models in the nature of accountancy can make things more critical whereas if the accountant or the auditors know the rules and regulation then the financial problems that the company is facing can be solved easily. By this means, the theme is described and so is quantitative analysis. However, with the help of financial activities, the companies can get more opportunities to invite various shareholders who can help them in their growth for future days.

6.2.4 Objective 4: To explore the process of adaptation of the IFRS in the UK

The necessity of chapters four and five refers to this objective as the financial advantage is depending on the process of adaptation by the company employees and the accountants. Without knowing the formula and the entire process of the IFRS and GAAP, no company can establish any regulation related to accountancy.

6.2.5 Objective 5: To assess the costs and other problems that may arise through the implementation of IFRS

In accordance with the theme 1 to theme 4 of the literature review, there is a significant difficulty in adjusting with the financial regiment criteria of reporting and making data sheets of the companies. Through the implementation of IFRS in accounting, several problems may arise due to the complexity over the cost restraints of the small scale and large-scale entrepreneur company. Balanced sheet has to be prepared by comparing the revenue collection of any company after the gradual reconciliation that has occurred at the beginning and the end of the financial year. However, in case of a company, the

authority and the employees have to face the interruptive legalized supervision of the government in terms of coercive isomorphism. Whereas in case of another issue faced by the company's employees to make the standardized data sheet of profit and loss ratio by keeping in mind the standards of other leading companies. Therefore, it creates the partiality in the data interpretation cases. According to the rules of IFRS, the interest received can be mentioned in either the cash flow from operating activities or cash flow from investing activities. These differences have created major confusions among the investors, and it has also impacted the profitability and equity position of the companies. New IFRS 16 changes performance indicators like EBITDA, cash flows and the effect of lease covenants, which creates an extra headache of calculations upon the employees of the company.

6.3 Limitations

The constituents of the global change paradigms of the consensus of current and previous financial recording become difficult to interpret by the application of IFRS. So this is also the limitation of the present context of this research on UK companies, which factor is missing in this review paper. The long distance prospect of this research cannot align the standardized setting of values, as different countries cannot adopt the low-demonetarisatation related solutions of IFRS. This is another limitation of this research.

6.4 Recommendations

Right foundation is to be chosen for implementing the complex rules and regulations of IFRS, so that, the specific company can relate the necessity of applying the IFRS with the required risk assessment of the company. For undertaking the post assumptive and presumptive sample values, the future research works should be progressive in constructing efficient operating models. Besides the shortcoming of the compromised accounting quality by merging the G-20 endorsed program with US-GAAP, the globalised standards of efficient accounting system can be ensured by following IFRS. The international organisations and stakeholders should be constantly encouraged to invest in the companies after comparing the report chart of the IFRS of different companies. More and more global organisations should be encouraged to invest in the international IFRS budget planning system.

6.5 Future Scope

I think that the trustees of emerging constituents of Asian-Oceania standard setter group (AOSSG) and Group of Latin-American standard setter (GLASS) are the two realistic groups. These groups are concerned with the benchmark setting of standard value estimation. So according to my observation, this will provide the future research scope with the collaboration of regional companies to conduct fieldwork or outreach programs. Financial lease assessment impairment or the problem of cash flow recognition and the insurance related problems can be the future prospect of research. Apart from these,

The Practical implications to all organizations implementing the IFRS in the UK

the more proven strategic implementation of the regression analysis or ANOVA testing of sample variance degree can be the optimistic scope of further research in this area.

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Name of the Journal : IFRS Implementation in UK Organizations

Title of the Article : IFRS Implementation in UK Organizations

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Date (mo/day/year) : 29/06/2026